

The Influence of Corporate Social Responsibility on Consumer Behaviour in South East Nigeria

Okafor, Joy Ndidiamaka

Department of Business Administration,
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka
nj.okafor@unizik.edu.ng
ORCID ID: 0009-0006-6934-2369

Nwosu, Ifeoma Chidimma

Department of Public Administration
Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka
Anambra state-Nigeria
ic.nwosu@unizik.edu.ng

Chidi E. Nwokike

Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University
Igbariam Campus- Anambra State-Nigeria
Department of Public Administration
nwokikechidi@gmail.com
ORCID ID: 0000-0003-3991-3379

Abstract: *This research paper examined the influence of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on consumer behavior in South East Nigeria. The study recognizes the increasing global recognition of CSR and its importance in integrating social and environmental concerns into business operations. While the relationship between CSR and consumer behavior has been extensively explored in various contexts, its specific impact on Nigerian consumers, particularly in the South East region, remains an area of interest. The paper emphasizes the significance of understanding consumer preferences and attitudes towards CSR for both businesses and policymakers. The research reviews existing literature on CSR and consumer behavior in Nigeria, highlighting the positive influence of CSR initiatives on consumer perceptions, buying behavior, brand loyalty, and patronage. It also recognizes the challenges faced by companies, especially small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), in implementing comprehensive CSR programs due to resource constraints and limited infrastructure in the region. Based on the findings, the research proposes recommendations to address the identified challenges. These include conducting targeted CSR education campaigns, supporting SMEs through collaboration and capacity-building programs, and assessing and addressing infrastructure limitations.*

Introduction

In recent years, the concept of corporate social responsibility (CSR) has gained significant attention across the globe as businesses increasingly recognize the importance of their social and

environmental impact (Agudelo, 2019). Corporate social responsibility refers to the voluntary actions undertaken by companies to integrate social and environmental concerns into their business operations and interactions with stakeholders. While the relationship between corporate social responsibility and consumer behaviour has been extensively explored in various contexts, its specific impact on consumers in Nigeria remains an area of growing interest. Nigeria, as the most populous country in Africa, represents a dynamic and diverse market where consumer preferences and behaviours play a crucial role in shaping business strategies (International Trade Administration, 2023). With the increasing awareness and consciousness of societal issues among Nigerian consumers, the influence of corporate social responsibility activities on their purchasing decisions has become a significant area of study for researchers, practitioners, and policymakers alike. Understanding the relationship between CSR and consumer behaviour in south eastern Nigeria holds practical implications for both businesses and policymakers. For businesses, a comprehensive understanding of consumer preferences and attitudes towards corporate social responsibility can inform strategic decisions, marketing campaigns, and product development efforts. Policymakers can benefit from this knowledge to create a conducive regulatory environment that encourages responsible business practices and fosters sustainable economic growth.

Consumers, being the most vulnerable community in the world, have become more conscious of their rights and privileges due to bitter experiences in their past purchasing actions (Potluri et al., 2020). They have often faced exploitation, especially in the developing world like south eastern Nigeria, where stakeholders lack a proper understanding of consumer rights and fail to provide adequate value for their purchases. This situation is prevalent across various sectors and regardless of the scale of the business. In recent times, consumers have gained significant influence and are actively asserting their expectations for businesses to take direct social actions. They seek responsible behaviour from companies and demand that they address social and environmental issues. Consumers now play a more prominent role in shaping the practices of businesses. Maignan (2001) aptly noted that consumer expectations and demands for socially responsible behaviour from businesses have been on a continuous rise. This trend signifies the growing importance of businesses to align their operations with consumer values and contribute positively to society. The need for businesses to prioritize ethical practices, sustainability, transparency, and social impact has become paramount. The call for direct social actions from the business community is a direct response to the desire for fair treatment, accountability, and respect for consumer rights. Consumers are seeking assurance that their purchases not only satisfy their needs but also align with their values and contribute to a better society. They demand businesses to go beyond profit-making and actively engage in initiatives that address social, environmental, and economic challenges.

A critical analysis of firms in Nigeria reveals a disheartening trend where numerous organizations fail to embrace the concept of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) and consequently overlook the potential positive impact it can have on their activities, sales turnover, and consumer patronage. One potential consequence of neglecting corporate social responsibility is the limited realization of high sales turnover for Nigerian firms (Ogar, et al., 2023). By not actively engaging in CSR initiatives, companies miss out on opportunities to build a positive brand image, enhance their

reputation, and establish trust with consumers. In today's socially conscious marketplace, consumers are increasingly inclined to support businesses that demonstrate a genuine concern for societal and environmental issues. Thus, organizations that neglect corporate social responsibility inadvertently alienate potential customers who seek to align their purchasing decisions with their values. The absence of a robust CSR strategy can hamper efforts to increase consumers' patronage. Nigeria faces various social and environmental challenges, including poverty, inequality, and environmental degradation (Osemeke et al., 2016). Businesses have a unique opportunity to play a significant role in addressing these issues by incorporating CSR into their operations. By actively participating in community development projects, supporting social causes, and implementing sustainable practices, firms can contribute to the overall well-being of society. However, the lack of emphasis on Corporate Social Responsibility by Nigerian organizations hinders progress in these areas and limits the positive impact that businesses can have on the country's socio-economic development. This research paper aims to shed light on a significantly overlooked research area within the realm of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), with a specific focus on examining the impact of CSR initiatives on the consumer behavior of Nigeria. Despite the growing recognition of CSR as a vital aspect of contemporary business practices, there remains a dearth of comprehensive studies investigating its influence on consumer behavior, particularly in the Nigerian context.

Conceptual Explanations

Corporate Social Responsibility

According to Carroll (1979), corporate social responsibility refers to the social responsibility of businesses and encompasses four key dimensions: economic, ethical, legal, and discretionary (philanthropic) expectations that society has of organizations at a particular time. Carroll's definition of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR), as stated in 1979, provides a comprehensive understanding of the concept. The Economic Responsibility dimension refers to a business's primary objective of generating profits, providing goods and services, and creating economic value. In fulfilling their economic responsibilities, organizations aim to ensure their long-term viability and contribute to the overall economic development of society. The ethical dimension of CSR focuses on the moral obligations and expectations that businesses have towards various stakeholders, including employees, customers, suppliers, and the wider community. It involves conducting business in an ethical and principled manner, adhering to high standards of integrity, and making decisions that consider the well-being and interests of all stakeholders. Also, the legal responsibility refers to organizations' obligation to comply with relevant laws, regulations, and standards set by the government and other regulatory bodies. Businesses are expected to operate within the legal framework of the jurisdictions in which they operate, ensuring compliance with labor laws, environmental regulations, consumer protection laws, and other applicable legislation. The discretionary (philanthropic) dimension of CSR goes beyond the basic economic, ethical, and legal obligations and involves voluntary actions and contributions that organizations make to society (Carroll, 2016). This includes philanthropic initiatives, charitable donations, community development programs, and other activities aimed at improving the well-being of communities and addressing societal issues.

According to Visser (2005), CSR involves businesses working in collaboration with employees, their families, the local community, and society at large. Visser's definition of corporate social responsibility (CSR) emphasizes the commitment of businesses to contribute to sustainable economic development while also improving the quality of life for various stakeholders. One key aspect highlighted in Visser's definition is the focus on sustainable economic development. This implies that businesses should not solely pursue short-term financial gains but also consider the long-term impact of their operations on the economy. Sustainable economic development involves ensuring the responsible and ethical use of resources, promoting fair trade practices, and contributing to the overall well-being of the economy in which the business operates. He emphasizes the importance of working with employees and their families. This highlights the significance of treating employees as valuable stakeholders and considering their welfare beyond the workplace. CSR practices that support employees' well-being may include providing fair wages, ensuring safe working conditions, offering opportunities for professional development, and promoting work-life balance. The involvement of the local community and society at large is emphasized in Visser's definition. Businesses are seen as having a responsibility to positively impact the communities in which they operate. This can be achieved through various means such as supporting local charities, engaging in community development projects, promoting diversity and inclusion, and being mindful of the environmental impact of their operations.

Consumer

The concept of a consumer has undergone a transformation in the context of global marketing. The emergence of the online consumer stage has revolutionized the way individuals interact with businesses, allowing them to explore, evaluate, and make purchases in a convenient and personalized manner. As businesses adapt to this new paradigm, they can leverage digital marketing strategies to effectively reach and engage this evolving consumer base. The term "consumer" traditionally refers to an individual or a legal entity that engages in the acquisition of tangible goods or services. However, in the current era of global marketing, the concept of a consumer has evolved, acquiring a new connotation. This shift in perspective is primarily attributed to the increasing prevalence of online platforms, which has facilitated the seamless transition from offline to online consumer behavior (Şerban-Comănescu, 2019).

Consumer Behaviour

Consumer behavior, according to Nassè (2021), refers to the study of how individuals or groups of people make decisions regarding the purchase, use, and disposal of goods, services, ideas, or experiences. It suggests that consumers go through three distinct modes: decision mode, examination mode, and evaluation mode, when considering products or services before making a purchase or repurchase decision. These modes are influenced by various factors such as choice, consumption, quality, taste, advertising, and price requirements and expectations. (i). Decision mode: This mode refers to the process consumers go through when making a purchasing decision. It involves gathering information, considering various options, and weighing the pros and cons before reaching a decision. Consumers may evaluate factors such as features, benefits, and price to determine the best choice for their needs. (ii). Examination mode: The examination mode suggests that consumers critically analyze the products or services they are considering. This

involves evaluating different aspects such as quality, performance, reliability, and functionality. Consumers may seek information from multiple sources, read reviews, compare specifications, or physically inspect the product before making a decision. (iii). Evaluation mode: After purchasing and using a product or service, consumers enter the evaluation mode. This stage involves assessing their overall satisfaction with the purchase. Consumers compare their expectations with the actual experience and determine whether the product or service met their requirements. Factors such as quality, performance, durability, customer service, and value for money are considered during the evaluation process.

Consumer behavior encompasses a wide range of actions, including the decision-making process that consumers go through when purchasing goods and services. These actions can include gathering information, evaluating alternatives, making purchase decisions, and even post-purchase behaviors such as satisfaction and loyalty. By studying these behaviors, marketers gain insights into why consumers behave the way they do and can adapt their strategies accordingly (Prasad, 2020). Prasad's definition accurately captures the essence of consumer behavior and its significance for marketers. By understanding the actions and motives of consumers, marketers can make informed decisions about product development, market trends, product obsolescence, and effective marketing strategies. This understanding helps them meet consumer needs, stand out in the marketplace, and build long-term relationships with their target audience. Consumer behavior, as described by Priest et al. (2013), consists of a broad spectrum of activities encompassing the cognitive, emotional, and physical aspects undertaken by individuals to satisfy their needs and desires by engaging in various stages such as selection, acquisition, utilization, and disposal of goods and services.

Theoretical Framework

This study extensively utilized Stakeholder Theory, a conceptual framework originally developed by Richard Edward Freeman in 1984. Stakeholder Theory proposes that organizations should consider the interests, needs, and concerns of all individuals or groups affected by their actions, commonly known as stakeholders. Freeman's theory posits that organizations are not solely accountable to their shareholders but also to various stakeholders such as employees, customers, suppliers, communities, and the environment. It emphasizes the importance of recognizing and managing the diverse interests and expectations of these stakeholders, rather than solely focusing on maximizing shareholder value. By adopting Stakeholder Theory, this study acknowledges the complex network of relationships between an organization and its stakeholders, and it examines how these relationships influence organizational decisions, practices, and performance. The theory provides a lens through which to analyze the impact of organizational actions on stakeholders and vice versa.

In South East Nigeria, applying Stakeholder Theory to the influence of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on consumer behavior entails considering the interests of various stakeholders, including companies, consumers, and the local community. CSR initiatives can shape consumer perception, as socially responsible actions enhance a company's brand image and reputation. Consumers increasingly prioritize ethical consumerism and may favor companies that demonstrate CSR practices. Implementing CSR can provide a competitive advantage by

differentiating a company from its competitors. Engaging with the local community and ensuring transparency in CSR efforts are important for building consumer trust and loyalty. Long-term commitment to CSR demonstrates social and environmental sustainability, leading to positive consumer behaviors and brand loyalty.

Method

This study extensively incorporated secondary sources of data. This implies that the research extensively utilized information and data derived from various credible sources, apart from relying solely on primary data collected by the researchers. The utilization of secondary sources encompasses information that has been previously amassed, scrutinized, and disseminated by esteemed researchers or organizations. Diverse secondary sources of data were encompassed in this research, such as scholarly books, academic journals, authoritative reports, online databases, and reputable news articles. By integrating these diverse secondary sources, the study gained a multifaceted perspective and enhanced its overall comprehensiveness.

Empirical Review

The collection of studies presented here focuses on the relationship between corporate social responsibility (CSR) and consumer behavior in Nigeria, particularly within industries such as telecommunications, oil and gas, retail banking, and GSM services. These studies provide valuable insights into the impact of CSR initiatives on consumer perceptions, buying behavior, brand loyalty, and patronage in the Nigerian market. Potluri et al. (2020) found that Nigerian consumers have adequate knowledge about CSR and that their awareness of socially responsible practices significantly influences their purchasing decisions. This suggests that Nigerian consumers have a positive perception of CSR, emphasizing the importance of CSR policies for Nigerian corporations to enhance their company and product positioning. Babatunde and Akinboboye (2013) highlight the increasing importance of CSR in Nigeria, where government regulation may be insufficient. They conducted a case study focusing on a telecommunications company and found that CSR initiatives positively influence consumer patronage. They also suggest that firms can achieve positive financial performance by investing in CSR activities.

Potluri and Raime (2018) further support the notion that Nigerian consumers have sufficient knowledge about CSR practices and that their perceptions of socially responsible actions significantly impact their buying behavior. The study suggests that companies should pay attention to how their CSR initiatives are perceived by consumers, as it can directly impact their market positioning and product sales. Akanno et al. (2015) examine CSR in the Nigerian oil and gas sector and highlight the varying levels of adoption among organizations. They suggest that organizations benefit from consumer buying behavior that heavily relies on CSR activities, particularly due to the wider dissemination of information facilitated by technology. Musibau (2017) focuses on the impact of CSR within the Nigerian telecoms industry, using MTN Nigeria Limited as a case study. The study emphasizes the need for MTN to further structure and expand its CSR initiatives, particularly in areas that directly benefit customers and host communities.

Akhigbe and Olokoyo (2013) explore the relationship between CSR and brand loyalty in Nigeria's telecommunication industry. They find no significant relationship between CSR and brand loyalty

but recommend integrating CSR policies into core operations and focusing on addressing Nigeria's socioeconomic challenges. Shehu, Bello, and Gimba (2022) investigate the impact of CSR on MTN's brand perception in Nigeria. They find that economic, social, and environmental CSR efforts significantly influence brand loyalty, suggesting that MTN should continue engaging in brand-building projects. Adeiza and Adepoju (2017) study CSR and consumer patronage of GSM service providers in Nigeria, finding that social responsiveness positively influences consumer patronage. They recommend enhancing consumer perception through independent assessments of CSR activities.

Amsami, Ibrahim, and Hamid (2020) examine the relationship between CSR and customer loyalty in retail banks in northeastern Nigeria. They find that CSR elements have a positive influence on customer loyalty, suggesting that implementing CSR initiatives is important for fostering loyalty. Qasim et al. (2017) investigate CSR as a marketing tool and its impact on consumers' attitudes and behaviors. They find that CSR can have a significant positive influence on consumers' attitudes and behaviors, enhancing a company's image and building corporate brand value.

These studies demonstrate the importance of CSR in shaping consumer perceptions and behaviors in Nigeria. They provide insights into how CSR initiatives can positively impact consumer buying behavior, brand loyalty, and customer patronage. The findings suggest that implementing CSR practices can contribute to companies' success and societal well-being in the Nigerian market.

Influence of corporate social responsibility on consumer behaviour

Studies have shown that the awareness of corporate social responsibility (CSR) in Nigeria generally has positively influenced purchasing decisions, helping companies enhance their CSR policies and product positioning. Potluri et al. (2020) surveyed Nigerian consumers and found that their awareness of socially responsible practices significantly influenced their purchasing decisions. This positive perception of CSR can help Nigerian corporations improve their CSR policies and enhance their product positioning. Additionally, Potluri and Raime (2018) investigated the relationship between Nigerian consumers' perceptions of CSR and their buying behavior. They found that consumers' knowledge of socially responsible practices influenced their purchase decisions, emphasizing the importance of CSR in the Nigerian market. However, these mentioned findings and others not included in this study may be valid in cities like Lagos, Port Harcourt, Abuja, Enugu city, etc. But in most of the towns in southeast Nigeria, where people buy things simply because they need them and not because of the company's corporate social responsibility posture, many consumers do not have a comprehensive understanding of the concept of CSR or its significance. This lack of awareness poses a significant obstacle for companies striving to effectively communicate their CSR efforts and positively influence consumer behavior. The absence of awareness regarding CSR can be attributed to various factors. Firstly, limited access to information and educational resources about CSR may contribute to the lack of awareness among consumers. In certain areas of southeast Nigeria, there might be inadequate dissemination of knowledge regarding the importance and benefits of CSR initiatives. This information gap can prevent consumers from making informed choices and understanding the impact of their purchasing decisions on society and the environment. The cultural context of the region may also play a role in the limited awareness of CSR. Traditional values and priorities

might not prioritize CSR as a significant aspect of business practices. In such cases, consumers may not perceive CSR as a crucial consideration when making purchasing decisions. This cultural barrier can impede the efforts of companies to emphasize their CSR initiatives and engage consumers in supporting socially responsible businesses.

Companies, especially SMEs, face significant resource constraints in implementing comprehensive CSR programs. This is particularly evident in south eastern Nigeria, where many companies operate as small-scale industries with limited impact on the local community. The lack of financial resources, expertise, and manpower presents challenges in undertaking impactful CSR initiatives. SMEs struggle to allocate funds for CSR activities due to operational costs and financial constraints. Additionally, they lack expertise in developing and implementing CSR strategies, hindering their ability to create meaningful change. Limited manpower within SMEs further limits their capacity to manage CSR activities effectively. As a result, SMEs engage in limited CSR activities, leading to minimal impact on the community and environment. This limited engagement can affect consumer perceptions and preferences, as customers are increasingly drawn to businesses that demonstrate social and environmental responsibility. SMEs miss out on the potential benefits of enhancing brand reputation, attracting conscious consumers, and fostering long-term customer loyalty.

The region of Southeast Nigeria, much like other areas of the country, grapples with significant infrastructural deficiencies that present numerous obstacles to the successful implementation of corporate social responsibility (CSR) projects. The deficiencies primarily manifest in the form of inadequate power supply, poor road networks, and limited access to clean water. These critical shortcomings have far-reaching implications for businesses aiming to carry out CSR initiatives in the region, hindering their ability to create a meaningful and sustainable impact on local communities. One of the most pressing infrastructure challenges in Southeast Nigeria is the chronic issue of inadequate power supply. According to Amudu et al., (2021), the Nigerian government's inability to foster an enabling environment has had detrimental effects on various sectors of the country's development. Frequent power outages and unreliable electricity infrastructure severely restrict the operations of businesses and the provision of essential services. Without a stable power supply, companies encounter significant obstacles when attempting to implement CSR projects effectively. For instance, initiatives that rely on electricity, such as setting up computer labs in schools or healthcare centers, become difficult to sustain and provide the desired benefits to the local community. The lack of power also hampers the deployment of technological solutions for education, healthcare, and other essential services that businesses may aim to support through their CSR efforts. The poor road networks in the region exacerbate the challenges faced by businesses attempting to carry out CSR projects. Inadequate infrastructure and poorly maintained roads make transportation of resources, equipment, and personnel time-consuming, costly, and often unsafe. This logistical hurdle creates significant delays and increases the overall expenses associated with implementing CSR initiatives. It becomes challenging to efficiently reach remote or underdeveloped areas, limiting the scope of potential projects and preventing businesses from effectively addressing the needs of local communities.

Conclusion

Received: 2 July 2023

Revised: 18 July 2023

Final Accepted 25 July 2023

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8180889>

This study highlighted the influence of corporate social responsibility (CSR) on consumer behavior in South East Nigeria. The findings indicate that consumers in Nigeria are increasingly aware of and value socially responsible practices by businesses. Nigerian consumers perceive CSR initiatives positively and consider them when making purchasing decisions. The positive perception of CSR can enhance a company's brand image, reputation, and overall market positioning, leading to increased consumer patronage and loyalty. However, there is a lack of comprehensive understanding and awareness of CSR in South East Nigeria, which hinders its influence on consumer behavior. Cultural factors and limited access to information contribute to this lack of awareness. Resource constraints, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), pose challenges in implementing comprehensive CSR programs. SMEs in South East Nigeria face limitations in financial resources, expertise, and manpower, making it difficult to undertake impactful CSR initiatives. These resource limitations restrict the potential for broader social and environmental changes and limit the influence on consumer behavior. The inadequate infrastructure in South East Nigeria, such as power supply and road networks, poses obstacles to the successful implementation of CSR projects. Businesses face challenges in sustaining CSR initiatives that rely on stable power supply and efficient transportation. These infrastructure deficiencies limit the scope and impact of CSR activities, hindering businesses from effectively addressing the needs of local communities. It is essential for businesses to collaborate with relevant stakeholders, including the government and local communities, to address these infrastructure challenges and create an enabling environment for CSR initiatives.

Recommendations

1. Conduct targeted CSR education campaigns in southeast Nigeria by collaborating with local organizations, community leaders, and educational institutions. Use workshops, seminars, events, and media outreach to raise consumer awareness about the benefits of CSR and its impact on society and the environment
2. Support SMEs in southeast Nigeria through collaboration among government bodies, non-profits, and industry associations. Offer financial assistance, capacity-building programs, and knowledge-sharing platforms to empower SMEs in developing impactful CSR initiatives and influencing consumer behavior.
3. Companies implementing CSR initiatives in areas with limited infrastructure should assess local conditions and collaborate with stakeholders to address limitations. Explore alternative transportation methods and partnerships to overcome logistical constraints and improve project efficiency

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